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Editors: Susan Schreibman and Vicky Garnett (TCD)

Contributors: Stefan Strathmann and Claudia Engelhardt (UGOE)
Ann Gow and Laura Molloy (HATII)
Jurate Kupriene (VUL)
Chiara Cirinná, (FRD)

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Executive Summary

In 2012, DigCurV Partners organised or attended National Meetings for the express purpose of promoting the activities of DigCurV and the Curriculum Framework development.

At each meeting, the rationale behind the lenses was discussed, and the uses of lenses themselves were explained

Many partners used the meetings as a means to promote DigCurV. UGOE suggest that their meeting ‘...served as a platform for the exchange of experiences...’ and highlighted how useful the meeting was for networking. Other partners found other useful feedback from the meetings, particularly with regards to promoting future events, discussing the Curriculum Framework in its current form, and using the CURATE! game as a means of raising topics for discussion.

This report will look at each national meeting in turn by country of the reporting partner. Details of the reports are presented in sections looking at the audience profile of the event, the outcomes of the meetings, and the impact of the meeting.

The report will conclude with a summary of the feedback and information taken from each meeting, and present recommendations for future meetings and work of the network.

1. Germany

1.1 “nestor/DigCurV School 2012: Practical experiences in digital preservation: formats, identifiers, migration” - University of Göttingen (UGOE), Göttingen State and University Library, Germany

Institute Organising Event	State and University Library Göttingen, Cologne University of Applied Sciences
Collaborating Institutions	nestor Qualification Consortium; DigCurV
Date of Event	22-24 October 2012
Venue	Akademie Waldschlösschen in Reinhausen, near Göttingen

Profile of attendees

Among the 34 participants from cultural heritage, scientific and education institutions were students, practitioners, executives as well as researchers and teachers.

Brief Overview of Event

Figure 1: Participants at the nestor/DigCurV National Meeting.

Image courtesy of Prof. Achim Oßwald.

qualification in the field of digital curation and preservation. In 2011, and again in 2012, the nestor qualification consortium organised the School together with the DigCurV project.

The nestor Schools are regularly held events of several days’ duration responding to the training needs of the German speaking digital preservation community. They are organised by the nestor qualification consortium, which is based on a Memorandum of Understanding between Higher Education and Further Education institutions in the German speaking countries that are collaborating to strengthen

When planning the nestor/DigCurV School 2012, we took into account the results of the DigCurV survey on the training needs in digital preservation and curation (see D3.1 Report and analysis of the survey of Training Needs) that was conducted in 2011¹.

One part of the DigCurV survey referred to the time frame and methods for digital preservation training that respondents regarded most suitable for their organisation. In terms of the time frame, the majority of respondents preferred short-term events of either 1-2 days or 3-5 days. The most popular training method was small group workshops.

The team asked the survey participants to indicate the topic areas where they thought the need for training to be most pressing. These were also taken into account in the planning of the event. The three areas where the need was indicated to be most pressing were general/ basic knowledge of digital preservation issues, preservation and data management planning and preservation tools.

nestor School events usually consist of several sessions. Each session starts with an introductory talk on the topic given by experts. Thereafter, the participants split up into small groups of 7-10 persons to engage in hands-on training sessions of 90 minutes. For each group a moderator and a minute-taker are appointed (the composition of the groups as well as the roles of moderator and minute-taker rotate across the sessions). Following the hands-on training sessions, the minute-takers present the results of the individual groups to the plenum and a discussion of the results and of questions that arose during the hands-on sessions takes place.

With the inclusion of exercises in small groups, the structure of the sessions corresponds to the DigCurV survey participants' most favoured training method of small group workshops. Also, the time frame of three days is in accordance with the preferences expressed by the survey participants.

The first session (after the opening session) was on PDF/A, session 2 dealt with persistent identifiers. The third session introduced the concept of linked open data. In session 4, the methods of migration and emulation and of tools used for these were explained and illustrated in a practical demonstration.

In addition to the four sessions, optional events offered in the evenings rounded out the programme. On the first evening, a university teacher reported on a student project dealing with the curation of digitally-submitted assignments and examinations. The second evening was dedicated to playing the DigCurV game. After a report on the making of the game in the context of the DigCurV, the rules were explained and the game began. Participants said they enjoyed the game very much

¹ There were 454 respondents from 44 countries (mainly European). The majority of respondents were affiliated to organisations of the cultural heritage as well as scientific and education sectors. Respondents were engaged in a variety of activities with regard to digital preservation and curation.

and found it a useful and pleasurable way of learning about digital curation and preservation. These activities as well as the meals provided opportunities for networking and informal exchange of ideas.

In connection with the nestor/DigCurV School, a focus group discussion was held to evaluate the DigCurV curriculum framework.

Promotion Activities

A website for the event was established containing information on the nature of the event, the programme, the venue, registration and contact information: http://nestor.sub.uni-goettingen.de/school_2012/

The announcement of and invitations to the event were disseminated via national mailing lists and the nestor-Newsletter. In both, the presenters pointed at the role of DigCurV as co-organiser and referenced the project website. In the opening session, we presented the DigCurV project.

Figure 2: Stefan Strathmann introducing the DigCurV project during the opening session

Image courtesy of Prof. Achim Oßwald.

At the DigCurV curriculum framework evaluation event, there was a presentation of the project and an introduction of the DigCurV curriculum framework draft before the discussion started.

Running Order

22 October 2012

11:45 – 12:15	Registration and Coffee
12:15 – 13:00	Welcome and Introduction to the nestor/DigCurV School 2012
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00 – 15:00	Lecture I: “Einstieg in PDF/A – Anmerkungen für Anwender“ (Introduction to PDF/A) Mario Röhrle, Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee break
15:30 – 17:00	Exercise I: “Einstieg in PDF/A – Anmerkungen für Anwender“ (Introduction to PDF/A)
17:00 – 18:00	Presentation and discussion of the results of Exercise I

18:30	Supper
20:00	Get together with a report on practical experience: <i>“Zwischen Anspruch und Machbarkeit. Auf dem Weg zu einem Digitalen Archiv für Prüfungsleistungen. Ein Studienprojekt.”</i> (Heading for a Digital Archive for digitally submitted assignments) Prof. Karin Schwarz, Fachhochschule Potsdam, University of Applied Sciences
23 October 2012	
8:15	Breakfast
09:00 – 10:00	Lecture II: <i>“Nachhaltige Referenzierbarkeit von digitalen Objekten mit Hilfe von persistenten Identifikatoren / Persistent Identifiers”</i> (Sustainable referencing of digital objects with Persistent Identifiers) Tibor Kálmán, GWDG
10:00 – 11:30	Exercise II: <i>“Nachhaltige Referenzierbarkeit von digitalen Objekten mit Hilfe von persistenten Identifikatoren / Persistent Identifiers”</i> (Sustainable referencing of digital objects with Persistent Identifiers)
11:30 – 12:00	Coffee Break
12:00 – 13:00	Presentation and discussion of the results of Exercise II
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00 – 15:00	Lecture III: <i>“Linked Open Data und Langzeitarchivierung”</i> (Linked Open Data and Digital Preservation/Curation) Niklaus Stettler, University of Applied Sciences HTW Chur
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee Break
16:30 – 17:00	Exercise III: <i>“Linked Open Data und Langzeitarchivierung”</i> (Linked Open Data and Digital Preservation/Curation)
17:00 – 18:00	Presentation and discussion of the results of Exercise III
18:30	Supper
20:00	Get together and playing of the DigCurV game “Curate!”
24 October 2012	

8:15	Breakfast
09:00 – 10:30	Lecture IV: <i>“Migration und Emulation – Angewandte Magie?”</i> (Migration and Emulation – Applied Magic?) Stefan E. Funk, Göttingen State and University Library
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 – 12:30	Exercise IV: <i>“Migration und Emulation – Angewandte Magie?”</i> (Migration and Emulation – Applied Magic?)
12:30 – 13:15	Presentation and discussion of the results of Exercise IV
13:15 – 14:15	Lunch
14:15 – 14:45	Closing and Evaluation
15:00 – 17:00	Optional additional event: <i>“DigCurV-Workshop zur Evaluation eines Rahmencurriculums für die berufliche Weiterbildung im Bereich der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung“</i> (DigCurV Curriculum Framework Evaluation Event)

What was covered

- introduction of the DigCurV project
- PDF/A
- Persistent Identifiers
- Linked Open Data and digital preservation/curation
- Migration and Emulation
- practical application: Archive for digitally submitted assignments

Impact of Event

The feedback on the event was very positive, both in terms of organisational and subject-specific aspects. As the analysis of the evaluation sheets shows, the participants were fully satisfied with the programme, the organisation of the event and the well-equipped venue located in an idyllic and serene area. All sessions gathered high marks for the selection of topic, presenter and presentation.

The nestor Schools are well-established training events in the German speaking digital preservation and curation community. The role of the co-organiser made the DigCurV project better known among the German community and increased the interest in the projects' work and results.

This interest could also be recognised among the nestor/DigCurV School participants. Stimulated by the introduction of the project during the opening session and by

playing the DigCurV game, many of them asked questions and wanted to know more about DigCurV and its work.

1.2 “Symposium Forschungsdaten-Infrastruktur” (Symposium on Research Data Infrastructure) - University of Göttingen (UGOE), Göttingen State and University Library, Germany

Institute Organising Event	Joint event of the DFG projects Radieschen, re3data.org, KomFor, EWIG, BoKeLa
Collaborating Institutions	Cooperative Library Network Berlin-Brandenburg, KOBV; DKRZ – German Climate Computing Centre; German National Library of Science and Technology University Library Hannover (TIB); German Scientific Earth Probing Consortium GESEP e.V.; Göttingen State and University Library; Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; Institut für Meteorologie, Freie Universität Berlin; Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT); Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences; Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP); Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics; PANGAEA® - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science; World Data Centre for Climate (WDC-C); World Data Center for Remote Sensing of the Atmosphere (WDC-RSAT); ZIH Dresden – Centre for Information Services and High Performance Computing; Zuse Institute Berlin (ZIB)
Date of Event	22 January, 2013 pre-symposium workshops: 21 January, 2013
Venue	Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam

Profile of Attendees

Symposium

There were about 140 participants. The audience included persons from research centres, universities and infrastructure facilities who are involved in research data

infrastructures and research data management on the research and development as well as the operational level.

Pre-symposium workshops

24 participants took part in the pre-symposium workshops, mainly researchers from the DFG projects Radieschen, re3data.org, KomFor, EWIG and BoKeLa.

Brief overview of event

The symposium dealt with the challenges and opportunities of the ever-growing amount of digital research data. The programme focus centred on research data infrastructures. In talks and workshops organisational, financial, technological and legal aspects of research data infrastructures and data management services were addressed.

One of the workshops was on qualification. In this workshop, the DigCurV project, amongst other initiatives, was introduced.

Also, a DigCurV poster (Training needs in digital preservation – A DigCurV survey [originally presented at the iPRES 2012]) was exhibited during the symposium.

Further, DigCurV bookmarks were distributed among the symposium participants.

In the pre-symposium workshop, working groups consisting of members of the involved projects discussed a number of topics that were also dealt with during the symposium. There was a working group on qualification, in which the DigCurV project was introduced.

Promotion activities

A website for the event was established containing information on the nature of the event, the programme, the venue, registration and contact information:

<http://www.forschungsdaten.org/uber-radieschen/projektveranstaltungen/symposium-forschungsdaten-infrastrukturen/>

The announcement of and invitations to the event were disseminated via national mailing lists and the nestor-Newsletter.

As DigCurV was not involved in the organisation of the symposium, it was not particularly promoted.

Running order

9:30-10:00	Registration & Coffee
10:00-10:30	Opening (Prof. Reinhard F.J. Hüttl, Spokesman of the GFZ Executive Board) Preamble (Dr. Stefan Winkler-Nees, DFG)
10:30-11:00	Keynote on Policy (Dr. Torsten Reimer, JISC)
11:00-12:00	Session 1 (talks and individual workshops were held simultaneously) Talks: Presentation of the projects Radieschen, re3data.org, KomFor, EWIG and BoKeLa Workshops: Qualification (Prof. Peter Schirmbacher, Humboldt-Universität Berlin) Data Management & Publication (Dr. Jens Nieschulze, Göttingen University; Dr. Harry Enke, AIP) Policies (Dr. Christoph Bruch, Helmholtz Open Access)
12:00-12:15	Coffee Break
12:15-13:15	Session 2 (talks and individual workshops were held simultaneously) Talks Private domain: Researchers and „their“ data (Prof. Frederik Tilmann, GFZ) Group domain: Data in Virtual Research Environments (Dr. Peter Bartelheimer, Göttingen University) Workshops Software solutions (Dr. Robert Hauser, FIZ Karlsruhe) Data publication and quality assurance (Dr. Michael Lautenschlager, DKRZ / Roland Bertelmann, GFZ) Costs (Dr. Henk Harmsen, DANS)
13:15-14:15	Lunch Break
14:15-15:15	Session 3 (talks and individual workshops were held simultaneously)

Talks

Persistent Domain: PIDs, digital preservation and certification – long-term availability of research data (Reiner Mauer, GESIS)

Public Domain: portals and best practices – making research data visible and usable (Dr. Hans Pfeiffenberger, AWI)

Workshops

Persistent Identifiers (Dr. Jens Klump, GFZ / Dr. Janna Neumann, TIB Hannover)

Data in Virtual Research Environments (Dr. Heike Neuroth, Göttingen State and University Library; Prof. Peter Schirmbacher, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin)

Legal Framework (John Weitzmann, Creative Commons)

15:15-15:30	Coffee Break
15:30-16:30	Summary reports from the workshops
16:30-17:00	Discussion and Conclusions (Dr. Jens Klump, GFZ)

Talks

- Private domain – the perspective of the researcher
- Group domain – virtual research environments
- Persistent domain – PIDs, digital preservation, certificates
- Public domain – portals, best practices

Workshops

- Qualification
- Data management and data publications
- Policies
- Software solutions
- Data publications and quality assurance
- Costs
- Persistent Identifiers
- Data in virtual research environments
- Legal framework

Pre-symposium workshop

- Qualification
- Data management
- Costs
- Software solutions
- Publications and identifiers
- Policies

Impact of event

The event brought together people from various institutions, who are involved in the field of research data infrastructures and research data management on the research and development as well as on the operational level. It served as a platform for the exchange of experiences and the discussion of issues and challenges in the field. It was also a good opportunity for networking.

The introduction of DigCurV in the sessions on qualification (at the symposium as well as in the pre-conference workshop) and the exhibition of the DigCurV poster made the project better known among the German research data community.

2 Ireland

2.1 “Realising the Opportunities of Digital Humanities” – Trinity College Dublin

Institute Organising Event	Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI)
Collaborating Institutions	Digital Enterprise Research Institute (DERI), Digital Humanities Observatory (DHO), Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH)
Date of Event	23-25 October 2012
Venue	23 October – Croke Park, Dublin 24 October – Royal Irish Academy, Dublin

Profile of attendees

This conference was aimed at a broad audience: leading experts in Digital Humanities and Digital Libraries, key policy makers, national funding organisations, students, archivists, and members of staff at national cultural heritage organisations. 274 delegates attended the conference in total, with 228 on the first day at Croke Park, and 134 attending the second day of the conference at the Royal Irish Academy. There were 27 stands demonstrating on the first day of the conference at Croke Park.

Brief Overview of Event

The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) Conference, “Realising the Opportunities of Digital Humanities”, aimed to engage academia, industry, cultural institutions and public bodies to identify the key research challenges in Digital Humanities. The proposed method for this was training of employees and fostering greater links between academia and industry in the adoption of DH skills, technologies and tools. In particular, how digital tools can enable better preservation, and how these tools can be used in the public sector demonstrating social benefit (for example, linked data and the Irish Census).

This conference had an international focus on the first day of the event. However the second day took the form of a national meeting, with nearly all speakers representing digital humanities and curation organisations within Ireland, with one or two experts from outside Ireland to add their perspective.

The event was jointly organised by the two major digital humanities national infrastructures (the DRI and the Digital Humanities Observatory), and the largest semantic web research Institute (DERI), together with a large-scale European digital infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH).

During the three days, participants engaged with practitioners from different areas of Digital Humanities through demonstrations and poster sessions, panel sessions with leading digital humanists and a series of workshops. DigCurV was represented through a poster and demonstration of the CURATE! game and a presentation during a panel session.

Promotion Activities

The DRI event was promoted through a variety of digital media. There was extensive email distribution, as well as a webpage with conference information that was available on the DRI site.

DigCurV was specifically promoted in this manner during the event at the poster sessions on Day One, and through a presentation by Dr. Susan Schreibman on Day Two. The presentation, which explained the work of DigCurV and offered a preview of the framework structure, took place during the 'Digital Humanities Skillset' panel session.

Running Order

DigCurV's participation was only on the 1st and 2nd day of this event – therefore only the agendas from those two days are included.

DAY 1: Tuesday 23rd October 2012

Venue: Croke Park Stadium, Dublin

Hogan Suite, 5th Floor

09:00 - 09:30	Registration, Refreshments, Demonstrations
09:30 - 10:00	Opening Luke Drury, President, Royal Irish Academy Sandra Collins, Director Digital Repository of Ireland Natalie Harrower, Manager of Education & Outreach, Digital Repository of Ireland
10:00 - 11:30	Panel 1: The Importance of Digital Humanities Why is Digital Humanities important and relevant? What are the challenges? What are the benefits being realized? Chair: Sandra Collins, Director Digital Repository of Ireland <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Curtis Wong, Principal Researcher, Microsoft Research• Fiona Ross, Director National Library of Ireland• John Keating, Associate Director An Foras Feasa, NUI Maynooth• Hans Walter Gabler, Emeritus Professor Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, Germany• William Kilbride, Executive Director Digital Preservation Coalition UK

- 11:30 - 12:00 Refreshments & Demonstrations
- 12:00 - 13:00 Launch and Address - Minister Sean Sherlock, TD
Mr. Sean Sherlock, TD, Minister of State, Department of Enterprise, Jobs & Innovation and Department of Education & Skills with responsibility for Research & Innovation will launch two documents of national interest:
- DRI National Report on Digital Archiving in Ireland
National Open Access Statement, prepared by the National Steering Committee on Open Access Policy.
- DRI Report Presentation by:
Aileen O’Carroll, Digital Repository of Ireland Policy Manager
Sharon Webb, Digital Repository of Ireland Requirements Analyst
- 13:00 - 14:00 Lunch & Demonstrations
- 14:00 - 15:30 Panel 2: Case Studies in Action
Organisations that are showcasing Digital Humanities; Novel approaches
Chair: Shawn Day, DHO Project Manager, Royal Irish Academy
- Múirne Laffan, Managing Director RTÉ Digital
 - Jon Purday, Senior Communications Advisor Europeana
 - Stuart Jeffrey, Deputy Director Archaeological Data Service UK
 - Hans Jansen, Deputy Director General National Library of the Netherlands
- 15:30 - 16:00 Refreshments & Demonstrations
- 16:00 - 17:30 Panel 3: Partnerships Achieving More
Academic-Public-Industry partnerships achieving more; Large-scale digital goals and challenges
Chair: Natalie Harrower, Manager of Education & Outreach, Digital Repository of Ireland
- Catriona Crowe, Head Special Projects, National Archives of Ireland
 - Peter Doorn, Director Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), Netherlands
 - Clifford Lynch, Director Coalition for Networked Information

- John Cox, University Librarian, NUIG
- Ashok Papat, Research Scientist, Google

17:30 - 18:00 Closing Remarks
Tom Boland, Chief Executive, The Higher Education Authority (HEA)

18:00 - 19:00 Wine Reception

DAY 2: Wednesday 24th October 2012

Venue: Royal Irish Academy, Dublin

09:00 - 09:30 Registration & Refreshments

09:30 - 09:45 Welcome and Introduction to Day 2

Laura Mahoney, Acting Director, Royal Irish Academy
Shawn Day, Digital Humanities Observatory
Natalie Harrower, Education & Outreach Manager, Digital Repository of Ireland

09:45 - 11:15 Panel 1: Intellectual Property, Licensing, Copyright
What you can and can not do with data
Chair: Seathrún Ó Tuairisg, NUIG PI for the Digital Repository of Ireland

- Mary Muldowney, Founding Member of the Oral History Network of Ireland
- Gary Davis, Deputy Data Protection Commissioner
- Eoin O'Dell, Chair Copyright Review Committee
- Andrea Martin, Irish Media & Entertainment law specialist
- Rónán Mac Con Iomaire Leascheannaire RTÉ Raidió na Gaeltachta

11:15 - 11:45 Refreshments

11:45 - 13:15 Panel 2: Semantic Web and Linked Data for Digital Humanities
Why would you use linked data?

Chair: Jodi Schneider, DERI, NUI Galway

- Stefan Decker, Director DERI, NUI Galway
- Silver Oliver, Senior Data Architect, BBC
- Michael Smethurst, Information Architect, BBC
- David De Roure, Director and Professor of e-Research in the Oxford e-Research Centre

- Anders Söderbäck, Stockholm University Library

13:15 - 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 15:15	<p>Panel 3: Digital Humanities Skillset Digital Humanities skills transfer; Industry perspective; Learning resources and skills assessment Chair: Sharon Webb, Digital Repository of Ireland Requirements Analyst</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Susan Schreibman, Trinity Long Room Hub TCD• Marie Wallace, Social Analytics Strategist IBM• Catherine Bruen, Manager National Digital Learning Resources (NDLR)• Aja Teehan, Technology Officer An Foras Feasa, NUI Maynooth
15:15 - 15:45	Refreshments
15:45 - 17:00	<p>Panel 4: Expressing the Value and Impact of Digital Humanities Research Chair: Luke Drury, President, Royal Irish Academy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Simon Tanner, Deputy Head, Department of Digital Humanities, King's College London• Nicholas Canny, Emeritus Professor NUIG & Ex-President RIA• Jennifer Edmond, Director of Strategic Projects, Faculty of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences, TCD• Eucharía Meehan, Director Irish Research Council
17:00 - 17:15	<p>Closing Remarks, Findings and Discussion of Digital Humanities Challenges & Opportunities Sandra Collins, Director, Digital Repository of Ireland</p>
17:30 - 19:00	Wine Reception

What was covered

Poster Session and Demonstration

The poster on presentation was entitled “What Has Digital Humanities Got To Do With Digital Curation?” (previously presented by Susan Schreibman at DH2012). This showed the general structure of the framework: in particular how the three lenses are related to one another, and the significance of each. In a large graphic at the bottom of the poster, the most recent draft of the Practitioner’s Lens was shown. Surrounding these two graphics there were call-out boxes explaining the background to the DigCurV project and the Curriculum Framework.

The CURATE! Game was laid out on the table at the stand and participants were encouraged to play the game. This proved popular, and worked as an ‘ice-breaker’ for participants who then asked further questions about the work of DigCurV.

At this demonstration stand, a poster for the ‘Framing the Digital Curation Curriculum’ workshop in Florence was also on display, in order to promote the workshop to those who might not necessarily be aware of it. Bookmarks with the full contact details of the DigCurV project were also developed and printed, and were available to participants.

Finally, a laptop was set up on the table, with internet access, to show participants the website and encourage them to join the network. It also showed them where they could download a copy of the CURATE! game.

Panel Session Presentation

The presentation delivered by Prof. Schreibman, entitled “Ahead of the Curve” further explained the rationale behind the framework. The background to the development, and the work conducted to establish the needs of the framework were highlighted.

Impact of Event

Through the poster and presentation session, many of those who stopped to play the game became interested in the work of DigCurV. Visitors to the stand included academics, and those working in the area of digital curation. In particular, an archivist from RTE (Raidió Teilifís Éireann- the Irish National Public Broadcaster), working in the RTE Archives was keen to discuss the background to the framework and how it might be used within the archive she coordinates.

Approximately 100 bookmarks were available at the demonstration stand and roughly half of these were left by the end of the day, indicating that approximately 50 participants had taken them for future reference.

Figure 3: The DigCurV stand at the Digital Repository of Ireland meeting

3 Italy

3.1 Cultural Heritage On Line “Trusted Digital Repositories & Trusted Professionals” - Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale

Institute Organising Event	Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale
Collaborating Institutions	Ente Cassa di Risparmio di Firenze, Library of Congress, Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage
Date of Event	11-12 December 2012
Venue	Florence, Auditorium di Santa Apollonia

Profile of attendees

Cultural heritage administrators and managers, digital humanities researchers and students, professional associations in the fields of museums, archives, libraries, funding agencies, technology providers and developers, cultural tourism operators

Brief Overview of Event

Figure 4 - Chiara Cirinná, FRD, presents the DigCurV framework

The third international Conference on Cultural Heritage Online was focused on trusted digital repositories and competences needed to manage them in the long term. Digital curation related to different contents and types of resources has become a fundamental element of any policy towards the future information society. Starting with the analysis of the trusted digital repositories and

the competences necessary to manage such repositories, specific attention has been paid to identify cultural heritage and digital humanities specific requirements, the role of standards, the importance of cooperation among user communities and user needs for training and re-skilling of professionals in cultural institutions.

Promotion Activities

The event has been widely promoted starting from July 2012 up to November 2012, in subsequent phases. The channels to promote the event used by FRD and by the 21 international supporters of the conference were: mailing lists, contacts, social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter); the DigCurV project has widely advertised the conference through its social media channels, the DigCurV network, and the project partners individual channels.

Running Order

12th December, Wednesday

- 9.00 - 9.30 Manuela Speiser, Research Programme Officer - European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
ICT Call 11: EU-funding for digital preservation research procured by public institutions
- 9.30 - 13.00 Session 5: Training and Re-skilling
Chair: Anna Maria Tammaro, University of Parma
Introduction to the session
- Chiara Cirinnà, Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale
DigCurV project: towards a Curriculum Framework for digital curation
 - William Kilbride, Digital Preservation Coalition
APARSEN project
 - Stefan Strathmann, Göttingen State and University Library, nestor
Digital Curation training - the nestor activities
 - George Coulbourne, Library of Congress
Digital Preservation Outreach & Education Program (DPOE)
 - Corinne Rogers, School of Library, Archival and Information Studies, The University of British Columbia
Digital records pathways: topics in digital preservation
 - Heather L. Moulaison, School of Information Science & Learning Technologies University of Missouri
LAM education for digital curation: A North American perspective
- 14.30 - 17.30 Session 6: Good practices and training provision
The selected projects are good practices of a trusted digital repositories and training. Session of presentation and poster, with a tour in exhibition area.
- Sabine Schrimpf, German National Library
The German National Library's test audit against DIN 31644 "Criteria for trustworthy digital archives"
 - Marcel Ras, KB, national library of The Netherlands
The international e-Depot to guarantee permanent access to scholarly publications
 - Sven Schlarb, Research and Development Department, Austrian National Library
A large scale data processing infrastructure for analysing large document collections

- Natascha Schumann, GESIS-Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
Certification of archiving procedures. Providing evidence of trustworthiness
- Juha Lehtonen, CSC - IT Center for Science
Towards preserving cultural heritage of Finland
- Eko Indarto, Data Archiving and Networked Services, Royal Netherlands Academy for Arts and Sciences
Text mining tools to support Trusted Digital Repositories
- Claudio Cortese, CINECA
The road (and the roadmap) for building Trusted Digital Repositories within an Interuniversity Consortium
- Francesco Nucci, Engineering
ASSETS project: a European success story
- Adrian Brown, Parliamentary Archives
Building trust: a collaborative approach
- Angela Di Iorio, La Sapienza Università di Roma
The trustworthiness side-effect for standardized description of the Submission Information Package
- Laurent Boch, Rai - Radio Audizioni Italiane
System and tools for a reliable management of rights information on audiovisual contents

17.30 Closing remarks

What was covered

The presentation illustrated:

- the actual context of staff involved in digital in Europe
- the EU strategies and investments for vocational training
- an overview of DigCurV (main objectives, start date, duration)
- founding partners
- the DigCurV network
- main activities performed at that date
- Curriculum Framework: the objectives, the lenses, the recommendations followed, the methods of its use, future developments
- the final DigCurV conference and the call for contribution
- the DigCurV multi-user stakeholder workshop in Florence
- invitation to join the network and contribute to the on-going work

Figure 5: Dr. Chiara Cirinnà previews the DigCurV Curriculum Framework at a National Meeting in Italy

Impact of Event

The event triggered a big interest in many participants, several people requested to join the network, others were extremely interested in contributing with a proposal to the call of the final conference.

4 Lithuania

4.1 “Digital memory in virtual space: projects experiences and perspectives” - Vilnius University Library, VUL

Institute Organising Event	Vilnius University Library
Collaborating Institutions	Vilnius University Faculty of Communication
Date of Event	17 December 2012
Venue	Vilnius University Central building (Universiteto g. 3, Vilnius) Senate Hall.

Profile of attendees

Sixty-eight participants and twelve speakers from four Lithuanian cities attended the event. The audience was quite heterogeneous, so upcoming discussions were more valuable. The largest part of attendees - Librarians (47), Museologists (7) and Archivists (8), together with individuals from Ministry of Culture (2), Association of the Lithuanian Society Genealogy and Heraldry (3) and Lithuanian Center for Folk Culture (4), represented almost complete cultural heritage sector. We also had 7 participants from academic institutions and 2 from CARARE project.

Figure 6: National Meeting participants at Vilnius University Library

Brief Overview of Event

The DigCurV National meeting ‘*Digital memory in virtual space: projects experiences and perspectives*’ was organised in a joint initiative between Vilnius University (VU) Library and VU Faculty of Communication. The event was held in VU Central building on 17th of December 2012. The aim of this national event was to discuss DigCurV activities, introduce project aims and main results as well to present other significant digitization and digital curation projects implemented by Lithuanian institutions.

Promotion Activities

Information about the event was promoted through several **websites**:

- VU Library website <http://www.mb.vu.lt/2265>
- VU Faculty of Communication <http://www.kf.vu.lt/lt/news/view/?id=4531>
- VU Institute of Mathematics and Informatics http://www.mii.lt/index.php?siteaction=news_notices.view&id=2943&lang=lt

- Vilnius university
<http://naujienos.vu.lt/ivykiai/konferencijos/25857-konferencija-apie-skaitmenin-atmint-virtualioje-erdvje>

Facebook and twitter:

- <https://twitter.com/Muziejai/status/276217402105135104>
- https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?id=378805249442&story_fbid=316610545114302

Direct invitations were sent through **emails** to professionals at national libraries, archives, associations, museums as well as to the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Lithuania.

Running Order

8:30 – 8:55	Registration
8:55 – 9:00	Opening and welcome speech J. Kuprienė; dr. R. Laužikas
9:00 – 9:30	Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe Project (DigCurV): experience of VU Library“ N. Klingaitė-Dasevičienė, (VU Library)
9:30 – 10:00	<i>“Lithuanian archaeology in Europeana: CARARE project experience“</i> I. Vosyliūtė, (VU Faculty of Communication)
10:00 – 10:30	<i>“Lithuanian Art Museum participation in international projects on the digitization and promotion of cultural heritage objects in 2011-2012“</i> D. Mukienė, (Lithuanian Art Museum)
10:30 – 11:00	<i>“The creation and distribution of solid content of Lithuanian Cultural Heritage“</i> Dr. R. Varnienė-Janssen, (Lithuanian National Library)
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 – 12:00	<i>“Lithuanian music in Europeana: archival audio records and virtual exhibition“</i> Dr. A. Nakienė, (Institute of Lithuanian Literature and Folklore)
12:00 – 12:30	<i>“Two projects in one, how to make supporting activity the key“</i> Ž. Jančoras, (Vilnius University)

12:30 – 12:45	<i>“Vilnius university library manuscripts in the World Digital Library”</i> E. Malaiškienė, (VU library)
12:45 – 13:00	<i>“National Museum The Palace of the Grand Dukes of Lithuania collections scientific research information system”</i> M. Kaminskas, (National Museum The Palace of the Grand Dukes of Lithuania)
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00 – 14:30	<i>“Lithuanian Documentary Cinema on the Internet (e-Cinema)”</i> V. Jucevičiūtė, (Office of the Chief Archivist of Lithuania)
14:30 – 15:00	<i>“Golden collection in LRT mediatheque”</i> M. Greičiuvienė, (Lithuanian National Radio and Television)
15:00 – 15:30	<i>“Thesaurus Latino-Lituanicus: Universal Latin-Lithuanian dictionary online”</i> Dr. M. Strockis (Vilnius University Faculty of Philology)
15:30 – 16:00	Discussions and closing

What was covered

There were 11 speakers who presented the most recent activities from various projects. Presentations were dedicated mostly to various aspects of providing cultural heritage content to national and international projects. Some also covered scientific research activities carried out on the basis of digital content.

Figure 7: The DigCurV Framework Lenses come under discussion in Vilnius

The VUL DigCurV team gave a presentation on DigCurV activities to disseminate and discuss the results emerging from the project, gather feedback about the Curriculum Framework and promote its usability.

Impact of Event

This event was a good opportunity to present DigCurV activities and also to gather feedback. The comments received were positive. The team received questions about the continuity of our project, future plans and possible ways of using the Curriculum Framework. All the participants liked the idea of expanding the descriptions. DigCurV received several invitations to present project results to various communities of cultural heritage sector during events in Spring 2013.

5 UK

5.1 “Aligning Approaches across Nations workshop, International Digital Curation Conference 2013” - HATII, University of Glasgow

Institute Organising Event	Digital Curation Centre (UK)
Collaborating Institutions	All institutions in attendance
Date of Event	14 January 2013
Venue	Movenpick Hotel, Amsterdam

Profile of attendees

An extensive network of those involved in digital curation research, training development and curriculum design from across the US, Europe, Africa and the Pacific Rim, including many in senior management positions. All have an expertise in Digital Cultural Heritage, including Digital Preservation, Information Sciences, and Software Technology.

Full list of institutions represented:

- Alliance for Permanent Access
- British Library
- Coalition for Networked Information
- CSC - IT Center for Science Ltd.
- Danish National Archives
- Digital Curation Centre
- Educopia Institute
- Fondazione Rinascimento Digitale
- Hacettepe University
- Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
- Joint Information Systems Committee
- Library of Congress
- Loughborough University
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology
- National Digital Heritage Archive, National Library of New Zealand
- National Library Board Singapore
- National Library of Estonia
- Netherlands Coalition for Digital Preservation
- Odum Institute for Research in Social Science
- Open Planets Foundation
- School of Information Sciences, University of Pittsburgh
- South African National Research Foundation

SURF
University of Glasgow
University of Leeds
University of Louisville
University of North Carolina
University of North Texas
Vienna University of Technology
W.A.C. Bennett Library, Simon Fraser University

Brief Overview of Event

This workshop provided an opportunity to describe and discuss the curriculum framework development of DigCurV in the context of other similar international efforts, to identify areas in which we can learn from the experience of others, align approaches across various international contexts, and benefit from discussion with an experienced specialist audience.

Promotion Activities

The event was promoted via targeted communication to named individuals recognised as being involved in significant work in this area.

Running Order

- | | |
|----------------|--|
| 9.00 - 9.30: | Personal introductions and overview |
| 9.30 – 9.45: | Brief summary of potential areas of alignment, based on discussions that took place at the two previous alignment events; |
| 9.45 – 11.00: | Lightning talks by selected members of the workshop organizing committee proposing specific, promising directions for alignment; |
| 11.15 – 11.45: | Prioritization exercise – participants will identify which of the identified actions are ones that (1) they could realistically prioritize within their own institutional contexts and (2) they propose as focus areas for alignment activities over the next 1-2 years. |
| 13.00 – 13.30: | Small group discussions devoted to planning and strategies for sharing and collaboration in the specific areas identified in the prioritization exercise; |
| 13.30 – 14.30: | Discussion among all participants about implications for collective action; |

14.45 – 17.00: Formulation of next steps, including: written products from this workshop, specific information gathering activities, plans for ANADP2.

What was covered

For DigCurV, Laura Molloy introduced the work of DigCurV to the audience, described the aims and objectives of the curriculum framework development, answered questions on the DigCurV project and demonstrated throughout the day’s discussions where the work of the DigCurV project contributes to meeting digital curation skills development.

Impact of Event

Discussions at the event will be formulated into actions by the chair, which will be shared by participants. This forum has already impacted on the work of the project, providing relationships with several initiatives which have developed work that the DigCurV project has been able to build upon; it is hoped that representing DigCurV at this event has raised awareness of the project in this arena and will in turn contribute to training being disseminated by members in the future.

5.2 HATII DigCurV focus group, HATII

Institute Organising Event	HATII
Collaborating Institutions	Digital Preservation Coalition
Date of Event	5 December 2012
Venue	University of Glasgow

Profile of attendees

Members of the teaching team at the University of Glasgow information studies postgraduate programme and the Digital Preservation Coalition.

Brief Overview of Event

This focus group was organised in order to gain expert input from teaching staff already engaged in curriculum development for the University of Glasgow postgraduate masters course, which includes digital curation instruction; and to discuss the requirements for the manager and executive lens as understood by the Digital Preservation Coalition.

The lenses were presented with contextual information to the participants and each domain was worked through with participants to gain detailed input and to explain the proposed usability and potential use cases of the framework.

Promotion Activities

Participants were specifically targeted by individual email messages. The focus group was framed as a DigCurV event, so promoting awareness of the work of the project.

Running Order

This event did not have a particular running order as the participants structured discussion.

What was covered

Participants engaged in a focused session going through each of the three lenses of the framework in detail, discussing content and structure.

Impact of Event

Teaching staff at the University of Glasgow Information Management and Preservation MSc programme, a major supplier of qualified UK practitioners in this field, is now aware of the work of the project and specifically the potential use cases for the lenses as teaching tools but also for the formation of future curricula.

The Digital Preservation Coalition, with its extensive UK-wide institutional membership, now also has a more detailed understanding of the DigCurV framework development.

6 Conclusions

The National Meetings by the DigCurV partners took various forms, but all served as a useful means of promoting and evaluating the progress of the project to date. Many partners reported an increased interest in participants who wished to sign up to the network following their national meetings. The work of the network was brought to a wider audience, and feedback was gained on elements of the framework and the lenses, which proved useful in its further development.

Feedback gathered

The partners reported receiving positive feedback on the development of the Curriculum Framework, with suggestions for its further development. VUL, for example, indicated that users would like to see further expansion of the descriptors within the framework, a notion that was also expressed by the participants of UGOE's evaluation workshop who discussed the framework within the context of qualification.

Use of CURATE!

The DigCurV game, CURATE! was used by UGOE, TCD and VUL during their National Meetings as either a means of engaging and drawing participants in to discuss the work of DigCurV, or as a means to 'lightly' discuss the issues previously raised during earlier presentations on the day. The success of the game can clearly be seen, even though it has only been in development over the past year. Further use and indeed development of the game should be investigated as this has become one of the projects biggest means of dissemination.

Promotion of the DigCurV 'mission'

All partners saw the National Meetings as an opportunity to bring the work of the DigCurV project to a wider audience. In some cases (UGOE, TCD and HATII) the meeting was held in conjunction with partners, some of whom are more prominent in their respective countries than DigCurV would be. By teaming up with these larger organisations, DigCurV was able to showcase the Curriculum Framework, and the mission of the project as a whole to this already captivated audience. Feedback in this regard came through numbers of materials distributed during the event, comments and request for information from the relevant DigCurV partner either during or immediately after the event or, in the case of FRD, through an increased interest in taking part in future DigCurV events, such as the Final Conference in May 2013.

Recommendations and future work

The reports from the partners all show that the name and work of DigCurV has been brought to a wider audience as a result of these meetings. Many with professional and personal interest in Digital Curation and Preservation techniques and training, from libraries to broadcast media archives, engaged with the DigCurV partners and either gave feedback on the current work, or expressed an interest in seeing where the project goes from here.

This feedback and interest indicates that the Curriculum Framework could be used in multiple circumstances; for individual professional development, or for recruitment of individuals. In terms of further development for the project, the responses seem to express a desire for an expanded version of the framework.

Use of the CURATE! game during these types of events is a useful tool for getting participants to discuss the issues at hand in an entertaining way, rather than through the standard formal presentation format. DigCurV therefore intends to use the game during the Final Conference in May.

Furthermore, as the CURATE! game has proved so popular, further development would be a great step for the DigCurV project, particularly as the issues raised within the game complement the Curriculum Framework so neatly.